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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D1.2 DMP - Data Management Plan

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D1.2: DMP - Data management plan	 <small>ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe</small>
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Nature of the deliverable:		Public
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP), is the formal document that sets out how the data will be handled during StandICT.eu 2026 during the Project duration and beyond.

The DMP therefore provides information on about the following aspects:

- The overall amount and typology of data the Project will generate;
- Ethical and legal compliance of the data;
- Secure storage and data back-up during the lifetime of the Project;
- Data preservation and availability for other usages (if appropriate) over the long term;
- How the project will ensure that data is well organised and adequately documented;
- Distribution of responsibilities for looking after data during and after the project and needed resources.

StandICT.eu 2026 has drawn up this document following the format of the recommended standardised online tool, Dmponline, from the Digital Curation Centre in the United Kingdom¹. Therefore, the sections in this deliverable follow the suggested template in the Dmponline tool.

As described in the DMP, the data collected by the project comes mainly from a free registration form to join the StandICT.eu community, to the following purposes:

- To apply to the Open Calls for grants, the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE).
- To join the EUOS – European Observatory for ICT Standardisation.
- To register to online events such Webinars in the context of the ICT Standards Academy or virtual Workshops.
- To receive the StandICT.eu newsletter.

Usernames and passwords are gathered in the registration facility of the StandICT.eu platform, which is not shared with anyone outside of the Project. Email addresses and other personal information are used by StandICT.eu to send specific communications to its community of users, such as newsletters, invitation to webinars and other events and similar community development and engagement activities.

Overall, StandICT.eu 2026 is in full compliance with the provision of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which has been in force across Europe since 25th of May, 2018.

¹ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/dmponline>

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
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AUS	Australo
DCU	Dublin City University
DMP	Data management plan
DMS	Data Management System
DSME	European Digital SME Alliance
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation
FACR	Financial and Administrative Coordinator Representative
FHG	Fraunhofer Society
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NDA	Non-disclosure agreement
OFE	OpenForum Europe
PMB	Project Management Board
TGP	Trust Grant Platform
TPC	Technical project Coordinator
TWG	Technical Working Group

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable, D1.2 “Data Management Plan”, released at Month 2, provides an DMP which involves the data structure and capture activities involved in the StandICT.eu’s web platform.

Furthermore, the deliverable describes the data the StandICT.eu consortium is expected to acquire and generate during the Project, how it will be managed, described, analysed, and stored. Furthermore, the mechanisms which will be applied at the end of the project to share and preserve the data are specified.

1.1 Relation with other Project Deliverables and Working Group(s)

This report mainly deals with the activities and project deliverables managed under WP3, “*WP3 Management facility for EU experts in ICT Standardisation “The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme”*”, which involves the set-up and maintenance of the Trust Grants Platform (TGP) to manage the cascading grant processes and procedures, as well as the plan and roll-out of the Standardisation Fellowship Programme.

Consequently, the related deliverables of WP3 are:

- D3.1 – Call monitoring report 1 (TRUST-IT)
- D3.2 – Call monitoring report 2 (TRUST-IT)
- D3.3 – Fellowship Programme interim report (AUSTRALO)
- D3.4 – Call monitoring report 3 (TRUST-IT)
- D3.5 – Fellowship Programme final report (AUSTRALO)

Further, the DMP also relates to WP2 Observatory and Technical Working Groups which involves the set-up, maintenance and evolution of the EUOS and for the liaison and concertation activities with international SDOs, and WP4 Standards Academy Programme, which includes hosting of standardisation meetings & workshops and synergising with other projects that have standardisation as an active task in their workplan.

Consequently, the related deliverables of WP2 are:

- D2.2 – Stakeholder consultation process mid-term report (DSME)
- D2.3 – Stakeholder consultation process, Final report (DSME)

Consequently, the related deliverables of WP4 are:

- D4.2 – Interim report on education in standardization (DCU)
- D4.3 – Final report on education in standardization (DCU)

1.2 Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- Section 2 addresses all the items required in the Data Management Plan in compliance with the table of contents of the Dmponline tool;
- Section 3 summarises the procedures followed by StandICT.eu 2026 to comply with the GDPR.

FIGURE 1 – PROJECT ORGANISATION

2. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

2.1 Preamble – Project Summary

StandICT.eu 2026 builds on the success of the previous two editions [2020-23 & 2018-19 StandICT.eu initiatives], delivered by the original partners who prepared the first proposal back in 2017, obtaining the recognition of the “go-to” project on ICT Standards in Europe. StandICT.eu 2026’s principal goal is to strengthen its global reach in the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem, by: a) launching & managing a robust and efficient facility supporting the Fellowship Programme with € 2,925,000 funding earmarked over 36 months with 9 Open Calls; b) EUOS (EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation) and Technical Working Groups (TWGs) empowering contributions from ICT standardisation experts; c) Training the next generation of ICT standardisation experts, engaging with National Standardisation Bodies & PPPs through the Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG); d) ensuring hi-level steering of StandICT.eu 2026 by means of an authoritative Expert Group (the EAG) who tap directly into the WGs & TCs of SDOs, tackling EU priorities, challenges & gaps; e) Creating an engaging & influential Forum on EU Strategy for ICT standards to address policy (FOREST), to keep momentum in policy discussions, in-synch with the MSP and subsequent high-level forum to be rolled-out in 2022.

2.2 Data Summary

Purpose of the Data Collection/Generation

At the core of StandICT.eu 2026’s architecture is the Grants Platform which provides and manages the processes related to the cascade funding, through three main services provided and accessible to registrants through a personalised Dashboard:

1. Open Call application platform, where applicants can enter and submit proposal for each of the 9 Open Calls of the project.
2. Open Call for External Pool of Evaluators (EPE), where applicants from different ICT fields can apply to become one of StandICT.eu 2026’s expert evaluators.
3. The Evaluation Workflow where the EPE carry out the assessment of each proposal submitted to the 10 Open Calls.

As mentioned above, these services are provided through <https://standict.eu/>, via a “Dashboard”; the “Dashboard” is only available to the user once they are logged in, and is dependent on user privileges and rights attributed on the basis on their role within the Project.

When registering as a user, the participant must accept the platform privacy policy. This Privacy policy is fully GDPR compliant, may be amended during the project lifetime and can be viewed at <https://www.standict.eu/privacy-policy>.

StandICT.eu 2026 collects the registered email address only to verify the account.

In addition, during this initial registration process, the user is given an option to “opt-in” to a StandICT.eu newsletter mailing list.

It is expected that there will be occasional surveys and public consultations undertaken for gathering feedback on the platform and these will be optional. The source data is not made public or shared outside the consortium. This data is used to generate summary reports only.

Relation to the objectives of the project

The StandICT.eu 2026 project has five key-objectives:

1. Deliver an evolved version of the Facility to support European ICT standardisation specialists;
2. Map ICT standards and foster a productive dialogue between policy, research, industry and SDOs;
3. Promote EU standardisation leadership;
4. Build the ICT Standards Academy to support the next generation EU Standardisation Experts;
5. Enlarge and further engage the already existing network of stakeholders to ensure maximum impact.

Since all these objectives relate to the methodology for collection of information from stakeholders during and after the project, they are all to a certain degree related to the topic of data collection and generation.

Types and formats of Data Generated/Collected

Data is free form data entered by users themselves directly into the Trust Grant Platform and EUOS, with the guidance of form fields, and help guides on the expected format and length of the information in each field.

Survey data will be in easy-to-fill tabular format to relate responses to questions. The EUOS section includes some public discussion areas that are freely accessible and visible by any user with limited editing rights only for registered users.

Furthermore, the EUOS will have a limited number of discussion areas with private access where selected users will be granted access to jointly cooperate for delivering a specific deliverable, such as the draft of "Landscape and Gap Analysis" in the respective ICT domain of expertise. The content of these areas will be neither accessible nor visible to other users.

Existing Data is always on-line and available

As mentioned above, the users are given dedicated and customised privileges, dependent on their role, and the information is always on-line and available, when needed. The source data from feedback surveys undertaken is not made public or shared outside the consortium. It is only used by the consortium for the purposes of gathering feedback to help improve the platform for future open calls.

Origin of the Data

In the case of user entry, the data is provided by the platform users themselves. The data will not be interfered with by any other users. As mentioned above, the users are given dedicated and customised privileges, based on their role.

Expected size of the Data

The entries to the Trust Grant Platform are guided for each field of entry required. The data could range from tick boxes, to single word categories to fields that would require up to maximum 1,000 words length.

In total over the lifetime of the project, it is expected that the entire data will not be more than 1GB. Personal data will form no larger than 100 MB (based on 20,000 users each with 50kB of personal data).

Data Utility

All the information gathered by the Grants Platform and the EUOS is to support the StandICT.eu project, the European Commission and the international community of researchers. This data will assist with finding partners, applying for funding, having applications evaluated and selected in a timely and efficient manner during the 9 Open Calls of the project.

If needed, survey data for gathering feedback on the platform consisting of anonymised summary reports to assist the consortium to improve the platform for future calls will be gathered. The data will be collected without using the personal data of the user.

The personal data of the users is not shared beyond the Project consortium members and EPE members for the assigned proposals only.

Informed consent form for marketing, and dissemination activities, events and public consultations

All users will be informed of the Privacy Policy and Terms of Use of the StandICT.eu 2026 portal at the moment of registration thereon and consent will be given through acceptance and compilation of the registration form.

2.3 Making Data findable, including provisions for metadata

Discoverability of Data

The Trust Grant Platform has been designed to allow the users to automatically discover their applications when they have logged into the system. Their level of discoverability is tailored and dependent on their privileges as a user, as follows:

- Open Call applicants: once logged in, they will have access to their own profiles and access to the current status of the proposals to keep track of any potential update.
- External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) applicants: they will have access to both an Applications and My Applications button. When the user logs in for the first time, they are given a choice to submit an application as an EPE or for the Open Calls. If they submit an application and are accepted onto the EPE, the My Applications button, will show their application and the Applications button, the applications assigned to them to evaluate.
- Selected and assigned EPE members: following the deadline of the call and once the submitted applications are assigned to the EPE members for evaluation, upon login they are given access only to the proposals they are assigned to evaluate in the TGP, or to perform Quality Control.

Approach towards Search Keywords

The TGP is equipped with a search functionality that is mostly used to find specific proposals more easily and/or users/applicants.

Approach for clear versioning

The TGP entries are date and time stamped, which will enable clear versioning of the entries themselves and reports can be generated, when needed (e.g. for purposes of gathering anonymised statistics, as required by the European Commission).

2.4 Making Data openly accessible

Data openly available

The textual and graphical data entered by the end users into the Trust Grant Platform in relation to the applications is only available on a need-to-know basis, and privilege basis, as described in section 3.3. The data will be made available in two forms:

1. The data entries themselves are openly available on the Trust Grant Platform itself, only for those with the privileges to view them, as described in section 2.3;
2. A PDF File of the contract will be shared with the funded applicant(s). Only personal data required in relation to capturing the identity of the signatories within the contract will be included in this output.

Methods or Software Tools to Access Data

The StandICT.eu platform has been developed using Drupal, a powerful CMS (Content management system), that allows a modern look and an appealing UX design. This platform was chosen since it has standard features that are functional and easy to use, such as content authoring, reliable performance, and excellent security. The Drupal Platform (made in PHP language) was found to be extremely flexible and modular, necessary for the purposes of the StandICT.eu platform. The entire platform is designed with a user-centric layout to facilitate access to the content and usability of the portal. Finally, the Drupal platform is a well-suited base to develop a GDPR-compliant TGP, which is one of the main goals of the StandICT.eu initiative.

2.5 Making Data Interoperable

Assess the Interoperability of Data

The data from the StandICT.eu platform will not be shared with third parties for any reason, except for our own anonymous statistical data. Therefore, the interoperability aspects of the data are not considered by the project.

Standard Vocabulary for all Data types

During the data entry process, the project team provides guidance to the users for data entry in terms of standard vocabulary and size of entries (number of characters or words) for all data types, as described in section 3.2.

2.6 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Data licence to permit the broadest reuse possible

When users register, they accept a terms and conditions of usage, where it is made clear that data added to the platform will not be publicly available, including their personal data.

Period in which data will be made available for re-use

The information and data input to the platform will only be regularly downloaded in an anonymised way (with no personal data) and summarized to be used for generating statistics, for monitoring the results of the open calls, such as number of applications submitted, where applicable. This will include data such as number of proposals submitted, number of funded proposals, number of different organisation types involved, total budget requested, typology of requested funds, statistics on the main ICT domains tackled by the proposal, geographical provenance of the applicants. From the perspective of open data available for re-use, as the project has recently started, we recognise that as the ongoing process develops over the project lifetime, it is our plan to review the type of data generated and which data belongs where in order to update the DMP, if necessary.

Data Production and Third Parties

Apart from the EPE members assigned to evaluate the individual proposals and the proposers themselves, this data will not be available, at any time, for usability by any other third parties, under any circumstances, unless it is anonymised, such as the statistical data mentioned above.

Data Quality assurance processes

The PMB which is comprised of members from each consortium partner of StandICT.eu 2026 and whose responsibilities includes all aspects regarding notifications for meetings, voting, quorum and formalisation of all decisions, will monitor the data with this important consideration in mind on a regular basis to ensure that the quality of the data is taken into consideration.

Length of time for which the Data will remain re-usable

It is expected that the data will remain re-usable for the lifetime of this project only. It is possible that the project may need to maintain the data beyond the end date of the Project, should the records of the Project need to be kept for review purposes by the European Commission services and independent evaluators, for a specific duration after the project is officially concluded. This duration would be based upon the specific requirement placed upon the StandICT.eu 2026 Project by the Commission as to storing the data after Project Conclusion

2.7 Allocation of resources

Cost estimation for making data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable)

The costs associated with the data is considered low, as the system has already been designed as GDPR compliant and uses tools that are both user friendly and provide the developers with ease of access for moderation. The efforts associated with ensuring the data is FAIR is taken care of primarily in the personnel costs of the project.

Responsibilities for Data Management

The overall data management in the project is the responsibility of WP1, "*Project management and coordination*", in close conjunction with the WP and task leaders in WP3, "*Management facility for EU experts in ICT standardisation "The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme"*". In addition, there are regular discussions in the monthly StandICT.eu's PMB Meetings about the overall data management. Trust-IT is the data controller for all data collected under the project.

The Data Processing Officer for Trust-IT is:

Mr. Michele Nannipieri, m.nannipieri@trust-itservices.com

Cost and potential value of long-term preservation

The costs involved and potential value would be considered relatively low, as the preservation of the data is not expected to be long term (see section 3.5).

2.8 Data Security

The overall Platform adopts security measures consistent with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect personal information under its control against loss, misuse, and alteration. In general terms, server configuration, https certificates, access controls, password storage and other relevant elements are dealt with in accordance to the provisions of the GDPR. We attempt to strike a reasonable balance between security and convenience. Emails are usually sent as unencrypted text. If misrouted or intercepted, an unencrypted email could be read easily. If there is a matter that requires high security or confidentiality, Partners are requested to please keep Trust-IT informed on the sensitivity of the information and request they not send the related information through email. The Project will take measures to prevent data loss and facilitate any security aspects related to the transfer of data and information, as required.

2.9 Ethical aspects

This project involves the collection of data from human participants and acts as the online portal streamlining the StandICT.eu application process. While we consider that ethical approvals may not be needed, we agree that the project is not free of ethical considerations. We identify the following, according to the ethics Horizon 2020 Programme Guidance on ethics self-assessment in H20202:

- 1) Confirm that informed consent has been obtained. Yes, it was obtained when the user registered to the site and agreed to the privacy policy. Item number 1 of the Privacy Policy is related to informed consent (see Appendix 1, Privacy Policy). Consent for any information that will be made open access will also be obtained.
- 2) Documents to be provided/kept on file: Informed Consent Forms + Information Sheets. These records are kept on record in the platform server, and can be inspected, if requested.

We will continue to liaise with the Institutional Ethics Committee to ensure that we are fully compliant with regulatory and legal requirements and submit a full application for ethical review, if required, in line with their terms of reference.

² [h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

3. PROCEDURES IMPLEMENTED TO SUPPORT GDPR COMPLIANCE

The following procedures and specific functionalities have been implemented and are continuously maintained to ensure compliance to the GDPR:

GDPR main points	Typical Drupal website installation
The right to be informed	Privacy notice webpage
The right of access	Usually all user data are accessible after login
The right to rectification	Usually all data are editable by the user
The right to erasure	It's possible to delete user account
The right to restrict processing	It's possible to disable user account, non-personal data generated by the user will be still visible but can't be changed anymore
The right to data portability	It is possible to provide data export in CSV format
The right to object	In the privacy notice: * You must inform individuals of their right to object "at the point of first communication" and in your privacy notice. * This must be "explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject and shall be presented clearly and separately from any other information".
Rights related to automated decision making and profiling	Usually no automated processing of personal data on Drupal
Accountability and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Implement appropriate technical and organisational measures that ensure and demonstrate that you comply. This may include internal data protection policies such as staff training, internal audits of processing activities, and reviews of internal HR policies. * Maintain relevant documentation on processing activities. * Where appropriate, appoint a data protection officer. * Implement measures that meet the principles of data protection by design and data protection by default. Measures could include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data minimisation; - Pseudonymisation; - Transparency; * Allowing individuals to monitor processing; and * Creating and improving security features on an ongoing basis. * Use data protection impact assessments where appropriate.
Breach notification	You only must notify the relevant supervisory authority of a breach where it is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals.

In case of data breach, the notification will be sent within 72 hours to Commission de la protection de la vie privée³, Rue de la Presse, 35, 1000 Bruxelles.

³ <https://www.privacycommission.be/fr/politique-vie-privee-et-disclaimer>